
STUDY ON TEMPERATURE COEFFICIENT OF REACTIVITY FOR PEBBLE BED REACTOR WITH THORIUM FUEL

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ABSTRACT

The pebble bed reactor has a flexibility to utilize a wide range of different fuel cycles without significantly modifying the reactor core geometry. These fuel cycles can be comprised of various fissile and fertile fuel isotopes. The purpose of this paper is to study the temperature coefficient of reactivity for pebble bed reactor fuelled by thorium. The HTR-Modul was chosen as the reactor model. A series of calculations was performed by the use of the Monte Carlo transport code MCNP6 with the continuous energy nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII. The k_{∞} calculation results show that the fuel load with a mass of 2g Th/pebble, 5g Th/pebble and 20g Th/pebble can achieve a critical core with discharge burnup of 65,644; 101,500; and 114,215 MWd/t, respectively. The calculation results of temperature coefficient conclude that specific mass of thorium per pebble might have a positive temperature coefficient of reactivity at a certain temperature. Further investigation needs to be conducted to analyze the behavior of these temperature reactivity coefficients in more detail.

Keywords: Temperature Coefficient of Reactivity, Pebble Bed Reactor, Thorium Fuel, MCNP6, ENDF/B-VII.

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1. INTRODUCTION

A lot of effort in international cooperation to define goals for the nuclear energy systems in the future and to select the key technologies for achieving them has been invested and made primarily through the Generation IV International Forum (GIF) in 2000. GIF has developed the technology roadmap as a starting point to identify and organize research and development of the new generation of reactors to be built around 2030 to 2040 with the criterions of sustainability, economics, safety and reliability, and proliferation resistance and physical protection [1].

The pebble bed reactor, a type of high temperature gas-cooled reactors, is one of the six classes of Generation IV nuclear reactors. It is moderated by graphite and cooled by helium. The graphite is primary material in the core structure and acts as neutron moderator. The helium is inert and does not react chemically with any material in core. The high temperature helium gas can directly power turbines to generate electricity at 45 percent thermal efficiency, compared to typical 33 percent thermal efficiency of conventional light water reactors [2].

The basic design of the reactor features spherical fuel elements called pebbles. The pebbles are made of graphite matrix which acts as the moderator and contain thousands of TRISO coated fuel particles. These TRISO particles consist of a fuel kernel surrounded by four coated ceramic layers for structural integrity and fission product containment. Thousands of pebbles are arranged within the reactor core.

The pebble bed reactor is inherently safe due to its physics characteristics, which increases neutron absorption if the temperature rises. Severe accidents causing core damage and radioactive releases is impossible to occur. The high temperature heat produced by the reactor enables efficient thermo-chemical production of hydrogen and disassociation of water into hydrogen and oxygen [2]. The reactor has a flexibility to utilize a wide range of different fuel cycles without significantly modifying the reactor core geometry. These fuel cycles can be comprised of fissile fuel isotopes of U-233, U-235, Pu-239 and Pu-241, and fertile isotopes of Th-232, U-238 and Pu-240 which are used in either mixed or separate form [3].

The purpose of this paper is to study the temperature coefficient of reactivity for pebble bed reactor fuelled by thorium. Thorium has been explored as an alternative nuclear fuel in thermal reactor to overcome the scarcity and the limitation of natural uranium resources. The use of thorium fuel in thermal reactor has been studied theoretically and the results have showed the advantage of thorium fuel in term of neutron economy and high conversion ratio [4]. India has been experimenting with thorium-based fuel in the form of uranium-thoria mixed pellets in the boiling water reactor (BWR). In several types of reactors such as high temperature gas-cooled reactor (HTGR), light water reactors (LWRs), and liquid metal fast breeder reactors (LMFBRs) a mixed thorium/uranium oxide has been utilized [5-12], but in pebble bed and prismatic reactors the focus was mainly on the use of thorium-based fuel.

A series of calculations was performed by the use of the Monte Carlo transport code MCNP6 [13] with the continuous energy nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII [14]. The HTR-Modul was chosen as the reactor model. It has been extensively used by some pebble bed reactors such as the South African PBMR and Chinese HTR programs as their reference model. Different thorium loadings per pebble were considered in the calculation as a function of fuel burnup to complete the analysis on the temperature coefficient of reactivity for pebble bed reactor.

2. HTR-MODUL REACTOR

HTR-Modul with thermal power of 200 MW was developed using the experience gained with LWR technology and the operation of the HTR reactor of the AVR power plant in Juelich. It differs significantly from the conventional water cooled reactors commonly operating in the world. One noteworthy difference is that HTR-Modul uses helium gas as coolant while water cooled reactors use water. Furthermore, HTR-Modul make use of graphite for neutrons moderation while water cooled reactors use either light water (H₂O) or heavy water (D₂O) [15].

A cylindrical core of the HTR-Modul has dimension of 300 cm in diameter and 943 cm in height. The core, which contains 359,548 fuel pebbles arranged randomly with a packing fraction of 0.61, is radially surrounded by side reflectors and axially by a top and bottom reflector. The reflectors are made from graphite and enclosed within a core barrel. The side reflectors contain numerous channels for insertion of control rods and helium flow. Helium enters the top of the core at temperature of 250°C, flows down through the spaces between pebbles and exits at the bottom of the core at temperature of 750°C. A thermal shield and reactor pressure vessel (RPV) surround the reactor barrel [16]. The fuel pebbles are inserted in and extracted from the core in a multi-pass scheme. If a fuel pebble is yet to reach its burnup target, it will be recirculated into the core, otherwise it will be sent to fuel storage and replaced with a new one. The parameter and core specification of HTR-Modul are given in Table 1.

Table 1. Parameter and core specification of pebble bed reactor [17]

Reactor parameter	
Thermal power (MW)	200
Helium inlet/outlet temperatures (°C)	250/750
Helium pressure (MPa)	6
Helium mass flow rate (kg/s)	85
Helium coolant density (g/cm ³)	4.33×10 ⁻³
Core specification	
Core power density (MW/m ³)	3
Diameter/height (cm/cm)	300/943
Number of fuel pebble per m ³	5,394
Number of fuel pebble in core	359,548
Pebble packing fraction in core	0.61

Figure 1. The schematic view of the fuel pebble geometry [18].

The HTR-Modul fuel consisting of thousands TRISO coated particles in a graphite sphere. Eachcoated particle comprises a (Th,U)O₂ kernel with U-233 enrichment of 7.48% surrounded by four coating layers of porous carbon buffer, inner pyrocarbon (iPyC), silicon carbide (SiC) and outer pyrocarbon (oPyC) to form the fuel pebble with a diameter of 6 cm. The radius of fuel kernel is 0.025 cm. The layer thicknesses of buffer, iPyC, SiC and oPyC are 0.0095, 0.0040, 0.0035 and 0.0040 cm, so that the overall diameter of coated fuel particle is 0.090 cm. The TRISO coating layers are designed as multiple defenses and barriers for fission product retention at temperatures less than 1600 °C. The schematic view of the fuel pebble geometry is illustrated in Figure 1. The specification of fuel pebble and TRISO coated particle are given in Table 2.

Table 2. Specification of fuel pebble and TRISO coated particle [17].

Fuel pebble	
Diameter of pebble (cm)	6
Diameter of fueled zone (cm)	5
Thickness of graphite shell (cm)	0.5
Density of graphite shell (g/cm ³)	1.75
Natural boron impurity in graphite shell (ppm)	0.6
Density of graphite matrix (g/cm ³)	1.75
Natural boron impurity in graphite matrix (ppm)	0.6
TRISO coated particle	
Diameter of kernel (µm)	500
Density of kernel (g/cm ³)	10.4
Coating layers	
Material	C/iPyC/SiC/oPyC
Thickness (µm)	95/40/35/40
Density (g/cm ³)	1.05/1.9/3.18/1.9

3. CALCULATION MODEL

The modeling of pebble bed reactor core cannot be separated from the treatment of double heterogeneity features. The TRISO coated particle consisting of fuel kernel and its coating layers creates the first heterogeneity. The pebble made up of thousands TRISO particles embedded in graphite matrix and graphite shell introduces the second heterogeneity. These double heterogeneity features can be treated by Monte Carlo transport code MCNP6.

MCNP6 can be accurately described as the merger of MCNP5 and MCNPX capabilities, but offers more than those two combined. High confidence in the MCNP6 code is based on its performance with the verification and validation test suites, comparisons to its predecessor codes, the regression test suite, its code development process, and the underlying high-quality nuclear and atomic databases [19].

Figure 2. MCNP6 model of hexagonal unit cell.

The modeling technique in first heterogeneity is to model the TRISO particle in graphite matrix with a hexagonal unit cell provided by MCNP6. This unit cell consists of 3 regions: fuel kernel, TRISO coating layer and graphite matrix as illustrated in Figure 2. Pitch dimension of hexagonal unit cell depends on the desired fuel loading in one pebble. Table 3 shows the pitch of hexagonal unit cell as function of thorium mass (m_{Th}) per pebble.

Table 3. Pitch of hexagonal unit cell.

m_{Th} /pebble (g)	Pitch of hexagonal unit cell (cm)
2	0.282824365
5	0.208386774
9	0.171308659
14	0.147848688
20	0.131275442

Figure 3. MCNP6 model of hexagonal lattice.

Figure 4. MCNP6 model of spherical unit cell for fuel pebble.

The modeling technique in second heterogeneity is to model the fuel pebble with a spherical unit cell. This unit cell is constructed by creating a lattice of TRISO unit cell as illustrated in Figure 3. The spherical lattice cell of the fuel pebble is made by modeling a 2.5 cm radius of the spherical fuel zone, which is protected by a 0.5 cm thick coating of graphite shell and surrounded by a helium coolant, as illustrated in Figure 4. The 3.53735 cm thickness of the helium is obtained by considering the pebble packing fraction of 0.61 in the core. Reflective boundary condition is applied to represent the reactor core of the HTR-Modul. The atomic density of (Th,U)O₂ kernel used in all calculations as shown in Table 4 is calculated with a simple formula.

Table 4. Atomic density of fuel kernel.

Isotopes	Atomic density (atom/barn-cm)
Th-232	2.19473×10^{-2}
U-233	1.76668×10^{-3}
O-16	4.74279×10^{-2}
B-10	1.14694×10^{-7}
B-11	4.64570×10^{-7}

The UNIVERSE and LATTICE geometry options are used in the calculation of temperature reactivity coefficient. The built-in CINDER module was also involved in calculating the fuel burnup. The modeling and calculation procedures introduced first by Lebenhaft [20] have been applied in various publications [21-31].

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The calculation of temperature reactivity coefficient was performed using 5,000 particles per cycle with active cycle of 200 and inactive cycle of 50. Initial neutron sources were located in numerous points within the kernel of fuel pebble. The continuous energy nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII was utilized in all calculations at room temperature of 300 K. The interaction between thermal neutron and all graphite contained in each reactor material under energy of 4 eV, which is known as binding effect, was considered by applying the thermal scattering library S(α,β) of grph.01t.

Figure 5. Change in infinite multiplication factor (k_{∞}) of thorium fuel in different loadings.

The change in infinite multiplication factor (k_{∞}) for fuel loading with a mass of 2g Th/pebble, 5g Th/pebble and 20g Th/pebble is shown in Figure 5. The value k_{∞} of 2g Th/pebble decreases with the increase in fuel burnup. The value of k_{∞} remains higher than 1.1 until the burnup reaches 65,644 MWd/t. The value k_{∞} above 1.1 is indicated as the limit of reactor criticality considering neutron leakage. The initial value of k_{∞} of 5g Th/pebble is smaller than those of 2g Th/pebble. The value k_{∞} of 20g Th/pebble is also smaller than those of 5g Th/pebble. However, it can be observed that the fuel pebble with mass of 5g Th/pebble and 20g Th/pebble can achieve the burnup of up to 101,500 MWd/t and 114,215 MWd/t, respectively.

Figure 6. Change in temperature coefficient of reactivity for 5g Th/pebble.

Figure 7. Change in temperature coefficient of reactivity for 20g Th/pebble.

Changes in temperature coefficient of reactivity as a function of burnup for fuel loading with a mass of 5g Th/pebble and 20g Th/pebble are shown in Figures 6 and 7, respectively. In each case, the temperature coefficient of reactivity does not show similar profile. Its maximum value does not appear at low temperatures. At burnup of 0 MWd/t, the temperature reactivity coefficient of 5g Th/pebble shows a tendency to be positive at a temperature of more than 634 K. Conversely at burnup of 50,000 MWd/t and 100,000 MWd/t, fuel load of 5g Th/pebble gives a negative temperature coefficient of reactivity and even more negative throughout the temperature considered.

With the increase in thorium loading, it does not necessarily mean that the temperature reactivity coefficient decreases. At a temperature interval of 760-1438 K, the temperature reactivity coefficient of 20g Th/pebble at burnup 0 MWd/t shows a positive value, while the fuel burnup of 50,000 MWd/t the positive value is achieved at temperatures above ~500 K and at burnup 100,000 MWd/t the temperature reactivitycoefficient of 20g Th/pebble tends to be positive throughout the temperature considered.

5. CONCLUSION

Study on temperature coefficient of reactivity for pebble bed reactor with thorium fuel has been conducted using Monte Carlo transport code MCNP6 with continuous energy nuclear data library ENDF/B-VII. The k_{∞} calculation results show that the fuel load with a mass of 2g Th/pebble, 5g Th/pebble and 20g Th/pebble can achieve a critical core with discharge burnup of 65,644; 101,500; and 114,215 MWd/t, respectively. The calculation results of temperature coefficient conclude that specific mass of thorium per pebble might have a positive temperature coefficient of reactivity at a certain temperature. Further investigation needs to be conducted to analyze the behavior of these temperature reactivity coefficients in more detail.

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